

Evaluating implement-induced CoG shifts on tractor rollover stability: A multibody dynamics and experimental study across different machine orientations

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ABSTRACT

Tractor rollovers are the main cause of fatal accidents in the agricultural sector, especially in rugged vineyards and orchards. Vineyard tractors operating in narrow passages are likely to lose stability due to high centre-of-gravity (CoG), sloping grounds and mass distribution. Current ISO standards cover lateral stability tests but do not take into account different orientations. The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of CoG shifts caused by various tractor-mounted implements on rollover stability of a narrow track vineyard tractor. First, the CoG position of a vineyard tractor was determined experimentally according to ISO 789-6 standards, and a rigid multi-body dynamics (MBD) model was composed by using Adams/View 2022.3 accordingly. Static Phase 1 stability tests were simulated using the PAC2002 tire model and pivot axle kinematics. The model was validated using a special rollover platform capable of testing $\pm 175^\circ$ orientation and 55° tilt angles. Results consistently yielded underestimated results (favouring safety) with a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 11 % compared to experimentally determined stability angles. To simulate stability changes influenced by implements, 13 different scenarios were analysed by varying the CoG position along the longitudinal, lateral, and vertical axes at specific rates in the MBD environment. The results were evaluated using stability maps and the Rollover Stability Index (RSI). The findings showed that lateral and vertical CoG shifts significantly affected the rollover behaviour.

1. Introduction

Agricultural workers often undertake multiple tasks simultaneously and work under challenging conditions. While the total number of occupational accidents in the agricultural sector is lower than in other industrial sectors, its rate of fatal accident surpasses that of all other sectors combined (Fagnoli et al., 2018). Hence, agricultural safety research remains critically important because many agricultural workers are unaware of the fatal consequences of such working conditions. The irregular terrain conditions in which tractors operate significantly increase the risk of fatal accidents in the agricultural sector (Abubakar et al., 2010; Mashadi and Nasrolahi, 2009; Hoy, 2009; Rondelli et al., 2018). Although tractor accidents occur less frequently than other traffic accidents, their consequences are far more severe (Arnal et al., 2017). In India, 31 % of accidents caused by agricultural machinery are due to tractor use, and 5.6 % of these accidents result in

fatalities (Gite et al., 2010). In Japan, the rate of accidents resulting from tractor rollovers is as high as 66 % (Wang et al., 2024b). Thus, passive and active safety systems have been developed to prevent fatalities resulting from rollover accidents (Benos et al., 2020; Gattamelata et al., 2021; Pascuzzi et al., 2020; Solovyev et al., 2022, 2020; Springfeldt, 1996; Wang et al., 2024b). One of the passive safety systems, the Rollover Protective Structure (ROPS), is among the most effective protective measures (in combination with the use of seatbelts). ROPS is a cab or frame system designed to protect the driver during tractor accidents (Alfaro-Lopez et al., 2024; Hard and Myers, 2011; Franceschetti et al., 2019; Franceschetti and Rondelli, 2019; Harris et al., 2011; Liu and Ayers, 1998; Khorsandi et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2015; Loring and Myers, 2008; Micheletti Cremasco et al., 2020; Pascuzzi et al., 2020; Reynolds and Groves, 2000). Unfortunately, often the use of ROPS systems solely relies on the choice of the operator, and not all the operating tractors are installed with it. For example, it is stated that only half of the

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tractors in use by 2008 are equipped with ROPS in US (Loring and Myers, 2008; Hoy, 2009). Nevertheless, there was no noteworthy change in these rates, and it is estimated that between one third to one half of the tractors still do not have it in 2022 (Sorensen et al., 2023). In Türkiye, 65.4 % of all tractor-related accidents are due to rollovers, and it was determined that only 19.6 % of the tractors involved in these accidents had ROPS (Gorucu Keskin et al., 2012). In Spain, only 68.3 % of tractors have ROPS, and 5.5 % of them were not suitable in terms of regulations (Jarén et al., 2022). Rondelli et al. (2018) also pointed out that almost 72 % of the fatal accidents were experienced by tractors with no ROPS between 2002 and 2012 in Italy. Apart from this fact, while ROPS increases driver safety during an accident, it does not have a function of accident prevention. Since the most effective way to prevent fatal accidents is to avoid them from the beginning, active safety approaches should be developed together with protective safety systems. Determining tractor rollover stability in advance will contribute to both the necessary design improvements for preventing rollover accidents and the development of active safety systems, such as early warning devices. Examples of active safety systems include those based on direct control of the steering system (He et al., 2023), integration of a flywheel system (Wang et al., 2024c), or a combination of both (Qin et al., 2021). However, the stability assessment of tractors should be conducted for all orientation angles in addition to the ISO standards, which currently consider only lateral stability tests to be sufficient, under sloped and non-uniform ground conditions (ISO (1623)1–2, , 2015). Furthermore, tractors usually do not work alone, but are used to power various implements. Implements that are directly mounted on the tractor body change its centre-of-gravity (CoG) (Lombardi et al., 2025). Depending on the type of implement used, the CoG position may vary along the longitudinal, lateral, and vertical axes, potentially having a significant impact on the tractor's rollover behaviour. These changes are even more critical due to the manoeuvrability demands of orchard and vineyard tractors which operate in narrow fields. The compact design of vineyard tractors implies that any mounted implement can significantly alter the CoG, thereby affecting stability. A measure called Rollover Stability Index (RSI) is used to determine the static stability of the vehicle. RSI is a critical parameter that characterizes the behaviour of a tractor in instability situations such as rollover, and it is influenced by many factors, including the geometrical features and mass distribution of the tractor, ground slope, and the wheel-ground static friction coefficient (f_s) (Abdulwahab and Mishra, 2017; Ahmadi, 2013; Arote et al., 2019; Liu and Ayers, 1999). Various approaches have been presented for RSI calculations, and these methods are generally based on experimental studies, simulations, and theoretical analyses. In experimental studies, real tractors are tested under various terrain conditions, and their dynamic behaviours are examined. In simulation studies, the dynamic behaviours of the tractor are analysed using computer models, and the effects of different parameters on stability are evaluated (Mazzetto et al., 2013). In theoretical analyses, RSI is calculated using mathematical models; recommendations are made for optimizing various design parameters (Arote et al., 2019).

Over the years, computer-aided methods have been increasingly used to assess tractor stability (Spencer and Gillian, 1976; Chrisholm, 1979a; Chrisholm, 1979b; Ataei et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2024b). Early multi-body dynamics (MBD) models typically focused on specific results of operating conditions, such as the manoeuvrability of tractor-equipment trains (Schneider and Fielke, 2008) or vibration analyses (Shahgoli et al., 2010; Zheng et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2022; Li and Liu, 2024). Later researches have also incorporated advanced simulation techniques for modelling soil interaction (Han et al., 2025), active safety systems (Song et al., 2022; He et al., 2023), and dynamic rollover behaviour (Yao et al., 2025), including obstacle-overcoming scenarios (Jang et al., 2022) with or without implements. Fundamental studies on tire-ground interaction revealed the decisive influence of parameters such as side slip and coefficient of friction on dynamic stability (Ahmadi, 2011; Li et al., 2015). The common goal of all these dynamic modelling

studies has been to reduce or eliminate the risk of rollover. This has generally been achieved through the optimization of vehicle components (Aoyagi and Matsui, 2022) or the development of active control systems (Qin et al., 2019). However, these models have focused on complex systems with multiple parameters rather than applying a systematic approach to investigate the effect of mass distribution on rollover threshold. This gap is particularly critical for narrow-track vineyard tractors where implement use can cause noteworthy CoG shifts that consequently influence stability characteristics (Bietresato et al., 2015). The objective of this study is to isolate the effect of CoG position on the rollover kinematics by controlling sliding behaviour. As is well known, the friction coefficient (i.e. related to the condition and conformation of the terrain) is one of the primary parameters which affects slipping/sliding phenomena (Gillespie, 1992; Milliken and Milliken 1994; Genta, 1997; Jazar, 2014), hence, excluding unpredictable effects of the terrain conditions will contribute to the understanding on the implement effect on stability. In a previous study (Carabin et al., 2025), we demonstrated that critical rollover occurs not at pure lateral rollover cases but rather at angles close to lateral orientation. This demonstrated that certification tests should not be limited only to lateral rollovers. However, a systematic quantitative analysis of the effect of CoG shifts on rollover stability across a 360° orientation range with an experimentally evaluated MBD model has not been conducted to date. This study aims to fill this gap by presenting a methodology that isolates the pure effect of changes in the CoG position on the rollover threshold. To this end, a rigid-body MBD model was composed in the Adams/View 2022.3 environment based on the mechanical properties of a vineyard tractor and experimentally validated using an innovative 2 Degree-of-Freedom (DoF) test setup. The sliding effect was suppressed in both experiments and simulations: a high-grip embossed grid surface was used in the experiments, while an idealized high friction coefficient ($f_s \geq 1$) was used in the simulations. Thus, the influence of complex variables such as soil mechanics was excluded to observe only the effects of the weight shift caused by implements. It focuses on a more general and fundamental conclusion by isolating the effect of the CoG across all orientations, hence, only kinematic effects of an equipment were evaluated rather than the full geometry of it. In the first stage of the methodology, CoG measurements of the tractor with no implements were carried out through physical experiments according to ISO 789-6 standards. A rigid MBD model was then composed accordingly. In the analysis, all bodies except the tires were assumed to be rigid, and the PAC2002 tire model was used. Critically, the model's validity was established through experimental rollover tests using a specialized test-rig with two rotational DoF (Carabin et al., 2025) to ensure that the model simulates real-world behaviour. To examine the effect of different implement configurations on tractor rollover stability, the validated MBD model was employed to incrementally adjust the CoG position without altering the mass. All scenarios were modified only in one axis, i.e., longitudinal, lateral or vertical. A total of 13 different rollover simulation scenarios were performed across the full 360° orientation range. The results show that lateral and vertical changes in the CoG position have a significant impact on the rollover risk, especially in lateral and near-lateral orientations, and that implements should be used with the utmost caution on sloping terrain. These findings provide the basis for the development of stability maps and future safety-oriented control strategies.

2. Material and method

2.1. Experimental methodology

2.1.1. Tested tractor

Vineyard tractors are specifically designed to meet the unique conditions of vineyards. Although they generally have the same weight as standard farm tractors of equivalent power, they must be compact and agile. Their limited trackwidth is designed to pass through narrow passages more easily; nevertheless, it increases instability and makes

them more sensitive to implement weight. The rollover behaviour of a tractor is mainly characterized by trackwidth, wheelbase, and CoG position as will be discussed in Section 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. Tire conditions and configurations are also important as the rollover moment occurs near the outer edge of the tire (Prevati et al., 2014).

New Holland TN75V, narrow trackwidth vineyard tractor, was examined within the scope of the study. The wheelbase and trackwidth were defined from the centre of the area of the contact patches of each wheel when the tilt (α) angle was zero, i.e., no longitudinal or lateral forces on tire contact patches. The influence of grousers was neglected, and it was assumed that the tire maintains a uniform connection across the contact patch. The tractor has a front trackwidth of 940 mm, a rear trackwidth of 860 mm, and a wheelbase of 2060 mm. An Ackermann mechanism is used to steer the front axle of this 4WD vehicle. When the 57-liter fuel tank is full, the weight of the tractor is 2355 kg with no ballast installed. The rotational DoF of the conventional pivotal front axle is $\pm 5^\circ$. The maximum load capacity of the three-point hitch for an implement with a centre of mass 600 mm from the pivot point is approximately 1800 kg. The mechanical properties of the tractor are given in Table 1 (Machinery Link, n.d. 2025).

2.1.2. Tilting-rotating test platform

In order to determine CoG location and perform stability tests, a testing platform located at the AFILab of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano is utilized. The logical design stages of the platform are described in detail by Bietresato and Mazzetto (2022). The initial design concept consisted of two tables that could be adjusted with actuators as depicted in Fig. 1.a. To test dynamic scenarios, it was also necessary for the vehicle (i.e., the tractor) to be capable of motion along a predefined test path. Due to the safety requirements of a driver, execution of dynamic tests is highly constrained. Moreover, this design requires a considerably large testing area, which makes it impractical. Therefore, they applied specific design improvements. Firstly, a circular part that can rotate around the z-axis was integrated into a single table. This single table was tilted parallel to the x-axis as shown in Fig. 1.b. This conceptual design allows investigating static stability across all β orientations. An actuator supports a single table to elevate and realize α slope angle. The scheme of the rotational DoFs of the final platform design is given in Fig. 1.c. Eventually, a turntable consisting of four individual sections with maximum dimensions of 6.4 x 4.5 m was developed to advance modularity and functionality. Each subsection has translational DoF along vertical direction independently, thus, realizes the height differences up to 300 mm among the wheels (Fig. 1.d and 1. e). The load cells under each segmented platform have a maximum load capacity of 5 tons (i.e., practically maximum 10 tonnes in total can be tested). The measurement of each wheel load under different slope conditions were carried out by virtue of these load cells surface in this study. The method was thoroughly discussed in a previous study

Table 1
Mechanical properties of New Holland TN75V.

Properties	Representation	Value	Unit
Mass	m	2355	kg
Wheelbase	wb	2060	mm
Front trackwidth	ft	940	mm
Rear trackwidth	rt	860	mm
Front tires	-	280/ 70R16	-
Rear tires	-	360/ 70R16	-
Ground clearance	h	240	mm
3-point hitch distance from rear axle centre	-	800	mm
3-point hitch height from the ground	-	700	mm
3-point hitch lateral (transversal) position	-	0	mm
3-point hitch lift capacity at 610 mm	-	1797	kg

(Carabin et al., 2025). The orientation angle β (maximum of $\pm 175^\circ$) is achieved through the use of a fifth wheel, while the slope angle α (maximum of 55°) is still provided by an actuator that rotates the central axis of the fifth wheel, thereby changing its direction relative to the gravitational vector. (Fig. 1.f and 1.g).

2.1.3. Centre of gravity measurement

The location of the CoG is one of the most important factors that plays a role in the stability behaviour of a tractor. Therefore, measuring it correctly is of critical importance in determining the stability behaviour of the tractor. The (ISO 789-6, 2019) standard recommends a series of test methods to determine CoG. Accordingly, the wheel forces are measured by load cells placed under each wheel, first on a flat plane parallel to the ground, and then when one of the axles is higher than the other at a certain angle. Although a single additional scenario is usually sufficient to find the longitudinal CoG, wheel forces from multiple slope scenarios must be known to find the lateral and vertical position. Jazar (2014) explained a methodology to calculate CoG position in each direction thoroughly. These methodologies also form the basis for stability calculations. The free body diagram of the tractor is given in Fig. 2. Here, wb represents the wheelbase, ft and rt represent the front and rear trackwidths, respectively. From the moment equilibrium of the wheel forces about the r1, r2, and r4 axes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -g_z & 0 & g_x \\ g_z & 0 & -g_x \\ 0 & g_z & -g_y \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} CoG_x \\ CoG_y \\ CoG_z \end{Bmatrix} = - \begin{Bmatrix} \left(\frac{F_{RL,z} + F_{RR,z}}{M} + g_z \right) \bullet wb \\ \frac{F_{FL,z} + F_{FR,z}}{M} \bullet wb \\ \frac{F_{RL,z} - F_{RR,z}}{M} \bullet \frac{rt}{2} + \frac{F_{FL,z} - F_{FR,z}}{M} \bullet \frac{ft}{2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The stability test platform described in the previous section is used to measure the wheel loads in this study thanks to the load cells placed under the platform surface, which allows instantaneous force measurement. Since it is also capable of orienting and tilting, wheel forces were measured in different slope scenarios to increase the reliability of the measurements. Wheel forces were obtained within all orientation ranges ($\beta = \pm 175^\circ$) with 15° steps for two tilt angle scenarios ($\alpha = 15^\circ$ and 20°). The position of the CoG was calculated for each scenario, and it was considered the average of all results. In this way, errors that may arise from unmeasured effects (e.g. effect of liquid movement, loosen parts, etc.) can be minimized. Carabin et al. (2025) thoroughly discussed the details of the methodology.

2.1.4. Experimental protocol for stability angle determination

The validation tests to investigate the reliability of the MBD model were carried out only for the initial CoG scenario with tilt-table experiments (Fig. 3.a and 3.b). As can be seen in Fig. 3.c, it provides hooks in every corner of the platform to attach the safety chains. During the experiments, two safety chain secure each wheel from the rims. The rear wheels were connected loosely to allow them to lift off the ground when rollover occurs. The front wheels were secured gradually tighter to prevent sliding and provide controlled tilting. The lifting of the front wheels off the ground occurs rarely compared to the rear wheels. This is due to the structure of the pivot axle and its kinematics, as explained in Section 2.2.1. In this way, the tractor was prevented from sliding on the platform for extreme longitudinal orientations which sliding likely occurs before rollover, and the initial position of the tractor was preserved as much as possible in each test scenario. In order to increase the adhesion with the wheels, the platform surface consists of metal grids provided with reliefs (Fig. 3.d). The fuel tank was full (i.e., 57 L) and the tire pressures were within the nominal range (i.e., 1.3 bar). The α angle at which any of the wheels lose contact with the ground was investigated by increasing/decreasing the orientation angle from 0 (i.e., for the forward orientation) in 15° steps within the $\pm 180^\circ$ range. The experiments

Fig. 1. A. Initial and b. improved design concept of the platform, c. rotational DoFs, d.,and e. translational DoFs, f. fifth wheel and actuator of the platform, and g. tilted and oriented platform.

Fig. 2. Free-body diagram illustrating the forces acting on a tractor on a flat surface.

were repeated three times for each scenario by gradually increasing the α angle. Unfortunately, as the slope orientation approaches the longitudinal direction, the tractor starts to slide before rolling over, and therefore measurements cannot be performed. Therefore, the tests were carried out in the orientation range of $\pm 60^\circ$ to $\pm 135^\circ$. Due to safety restrictions, unpredictable variables and the impossibility of making changes on the test sample, the model was validated only for the initial CoG value.

2.2. Numerical modelling and simulations

2.2.1. Theoretical foundations of rollover stability

Considering the environmental conditions in which they operate, tractors must have high ground clearance (Stoyanov, 2024). This unfortunately results in a higher positioning of the CoG. Nevertheless, the lower vertical position of the CoG ensures a higher level of stability. A wider trackwidth also improves stability behaviour (Reimpell, 1989). It should be noted that as the wheelbase is wider than the trackwidth, the limited instability angle of the longitudinal/near-longitudinal orientations exceeds that of lateral and near-lateral rollovers (Previati et al.,

Fig. 3. A. and b. Phase 1 stability tests, c. safety hooks and chains, and d. metal grid surface of the platform.

2014). Additionally, operating conditions, including terrain slope, ground conditions, speed, and load, significantly affect tractor stability. Especially in regions where the ground conditions are less predictable, such as mountainous areas, land inhomogeneity or non-uniform ground hardness can change the direction of the mass vector unpredictably, thereby increasing instability.

Each vehicle is equipped with a suitable mechanism to adapt to the specific terrain conditions and handling requirements expected in each class. A pivotal front axle is utilized to improve handling and traction characteristics of a tractor. In this mechanism, the relative rotational motion between the axle and the body is enabled by the pivot – a passive revolute joint with a single rotational DoF in the longitudinal direction (i.e., x-axis), typically positioned in the lateral mid-plane of the tractor. The DoF is limited by the bump stops positioned on either side of the axle; in other words, the mechanical range of the angular displacement θ is confined to the range between upper and lower bump stops on each side. This angular DoF requires the stability behaviour of tractors to be analysed in two distinct phases. When θ is below a certain value (e.g., 5° for the tractor tested in this paper), the system is evaluated in Phase 1 stability (Li et al., 2016). In this phase, the instability moment will occur around the edges of the triangle formed by the pivot and the ground contact points of the rear wheels as depicted in Fig. 4. When one of the bumpstop pairs comes into contact, i.e., θ reaches its maximum value, the relative motion between the body and the axle is restricted, and the

Fig. 4. Stability region for Phase I stability mode.

tractor is evaluated using the Phase 2 stability model (Previati et al., 2014). Phase 1 instability is examined in this study.

In order to better define the concept of stability and thus understand the rollover theory, the initial condition where the tractor stands on a flat surface parallel to the ground, i.e., under ideal stability, should be considered. When the CoG is defined, the total mass can be represented as a point load at that location. On a horizontal plane and under stationary conditions, the tractor has a mass m and a corresponding weight

force $G = m \cdot g$. The four reaction forces transmitted to the ground by the tires are denoted as $F_{i,j}$, where i represents the front (F) or rear (R) axle force, and j represents the left (L) or right (R) wheel force. When the equilibrium of total forces is taken into account, the relationship between $F_{i,j}$ and G can be expressed as follows:

$$G = \sum_{i=F,R} \sum_{j=L,R} F_{i,j} \quad (2)$$

When the tractor begins to tilt in any direction, the load on the wheels that are elevated above the others gradually decreases. Simultaneously, the direction of the resultant force (G) shifts and tends to approach the hinge point of the stability triangle (i.e., rear wheel contact points and the pivotal joint). As shown in Fig. 5, for a pure lateral rollover scenario with a laterally symmetric CoG and equal front and rear trackwidth (tw), α_{lim} can be expressed as:

$$\alpha_{lim} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{tw/2}{CoG_z} \right) \quad (3)$$

This proves that both the vertical and lateral positions of the CoG affect lateral rollover behaviour. For example, a lateral CoG shift directly impacts the rollover threshold by increasing or decreasing the moment arm. It should be noted that this equation is only valid for lateral rollover. A similar effect is observed for longitudinal CoG shifts in longitudinal or near-longitudinal rollover scenarios. However, to be able to estimate rollover behaviour apart from lateral, other methodologies (e.g. analytical, simulation, etc.) should be employed (Belloni et al., 2024; Carabin et al., 2024; Previati et al., 2014).

2.2.2. Rollover stability index (RSI)

The basic equations used in calculating RSI are generally based on the analysis of the forces that balance the overturning moment (Bietresato et al., 2015). For example, to evaluate the lateral stability of a tractor, an equation is used that considers the location of the CoG and the lateral slope angle. This equation shows that the risk of overturning increases when the vertical line passing through the CoG shifts beyond half the trackwidth of the tractor (assuming a laterally symmetric CoG position). As seen in Fig. 5, the two basic factors affecting lateral overturning are the vertical and lateral locations of the CoG. It should be noted that stability is influenced by the combination of the slope angle (α) and the tractor's moving direction (β), which may interact in complex ways. While static equilibrium conditions of the tractor are examined for the static RSI value, the forces and moments to which the tractor is exposed while in motion are taken into account for the dynamic RSI. The factors that affect static RSI can be seen in Table 2. Static RSI might have a value between 0 and 100. It is equal to 100 when the vehicle is parallel to the ground. When it is equal to zero, the overturning

Table 2

Tractor features that influence steady-state rollover stability of a tractor.

Stability type	Factors	Representation
Static lateral rollover stability	Lateral CoG position	CoG _y
	Vertical CoG position	CoG _z
	Trackwidth	tw
	Tire width	–
Static longitudinal rollover stability	Longitudinal CoG position	CoG _x
	Vertical CoG position	CoG _z
	Wheelbase	wb
	Tire sizes	–

movement starts. RSI can be expressed as (Vidoni et al., 2015):

$$RSI = \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{\alpha_{crit}} \right) \times 100 \begin{cases} \alpha \in [0; \alpha_{crit}[: \text{stability satisfied} \\ \alpha = \alpha_{crit} : \text{critical overturning moment} \\ \alpha > \alpha_{crit} : \text{overturning occurred} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

2.2.3. Stability map

Stability maps, which are widely used to visualize tractor stability, were used to illustrate the measurements. These maps are used to characterize different orientations of vehicles on sloped terrain. A stability map is simply a polar diagram consisting of two coordinates. The angular coordinate represents the orientation angle (β), while the radial coordinate represents the terrain slope (α). The value $\beta = +90^\circ$ stands for the lateral inclination of the tractor to the right, $\beta = -90^\circ$ stands for the left inclination, $\beta = 0^\circ$ is the uphill direction, and $\beta = \pm 180^\circ$ is the downhill direction. Three basic regions are depicted in this diagram: the extended left and right-side rollover regions (blue and red areas in Fig. 6, respectively), and the extended longitudinal rollover regions (grey areas). Here, the continuous lines show the rollover region results and the dotted lines show the sliding region results of the MBD simulations, while the experimental measurements are expressed as dots. The real-world tests for the initial CoG condition can only be performed in a certain orientation range due to mechanical constraints (sliding on the platform). This area can be expanded by changing the friction coefficient in the MBD analyses.

2.2.4. Boundary conditions and assumptions of the MBD model

To increase the accuracy of stability estimates, it is of great importance to correctly evaluate the effects of critical elements under different conditions during the design phase. Although experiments are the most reliable means of determining the actual rollover angle of the tractor, they are excessively time-consuming. Additionally, the test platform has some mechanical limitations. For example, due to the friction limit and the tilt angle range of the platform, the tractor starts to slide before it

Fig. 5. Lateral stability condition of a tractor a. before rollover, b. at critical overturning moment, and c. after rollover.

Fig. 6. Stability map example.

rolls over after certain orientation angles. Obtaining some features such as tire behaviour by experimental methods also requires special equipment and is quite laborious (Kulikowski and Szpica, 2014; Liang et al., 2020). MBD method can model such variables in a realistic way. MBD theory performs energy calculations based on the mass and inertia values of objects in space. It restricts the motion and satisfies the connection between rigid bodies with kinematic constraints (contacts, joints, etc.). These constraints determine the translational and rotational DoFs of the overall system. Each connection generates force and moment. The methodology basically depends on examining the kinetic energy change caused by these forces and moments on the motion of the mechanism (Amirouche, 2006; Blundell and Harty, 2015; Shabana, 1989; Woernle, 2024). The MBD model and its boundary conditions are given in Fig. 7. All bodies (i.e., front and rear axle, and body) except the tires are assumed to be rigid. The $\pm 180^\circ$ orientation range (β) of the platform is provided by the revolute joint B. The revolute joint A simulates the tilt angle (α), and its limit is 75° . The entire system is subjected to gravitational force acting along the vehicle's vertical axis in its initial configuration, where all revolute joints have zero angular displacement. The platform surface is flat. In order for the model to be used to examine potholes/bumps and helicoidal paths that can be encountered on the

terrain conditions, the platform consists of four equal surfaces that have independent translational DoFs in the vertical direction up to 300 mm. Since this study examines the quasi-static Phase 1 instability tests of tractors, the kinematic effect of the pivot centre of rotation can be neglected. A low relative movement may occur between the body and the axle with increasing terrain slope; however, there will be no sudden inertia change as in dynamic conditions. In other words, there is no sudden shift from Phase 1 to Phase 2 of the stability state, which eliminates the kinematic effects of the pivotal axle on stability during the analyses. Hence, due to the difficulty of measuring its real position and the possibility of unreliability of the measurements, the pivot was modelled as the revolute joint P on the axis formed by the front wheel centres. Its rotational DoF (θ) occurs around the x-axis and is limited to $\pm 5^\circ$. The moment of inertia values of the system elements were not considered, as the model was quasistatic, and the total vehicle mass is defined as a point load at the CoG position of the current analysis scenario.

2.2.5. Simulation settings and numerical solutions

An MBD model that can simulate quasi-static stability tests was composed in the Adams/View 2022.3 environment to investigate the effect of different CoG locations as a result of different implements on stability. Adams is a multi-body dynamics software that uses various integration methods to solve systems with multiple DoFs. It successfully estimates the unknown parameters according to the initial condition, DoFs, and boundary conditions. Its solver is based on the initial forces, damping and stiffness coefficient of elastic connections, and the friction coefficients. In this study, STIFF integration method which is a concept used to solve ordinary differential equations was adopted. Adams basically implements GSTIFF (Gear Stiff) and WSTIFF (Wrapped Stiff) methods to solve closed-loop and open-loop mechanisms' differential equations respectively. These differential equations describe a multi-component system that varies on different time scales. They model complex systems such as tractor dynamics with considerably sudden tire-ground contact effects and relatively slow rolling motion. In such systems, simple integration methods (e.g., the explicit Euler method) are unstable which leads the numerical solution to reach infinity. To eliminate this problem, implicit integrators must be adopted to prevent accuracy of the solution. WSTIFF integration method was utilized in the scope of this study instead of GSTIFF method as the kinematic structure of the simulation constitutes an open-loop system. WSTIFF method applies a coordinate reduction formulation to handle high-frequency

Fig. 7. MBD model structure and boundary conditions in stability analysis.

numerical oscillations (Hairer and Wanner, 1991). The I3 formulation was selected for its ability to handle algebraic constraint equations besides the differential equations of motion (Hexagon, 2023). This combination (WSTIFF and I3) is robust for simulating systems with abrupt changes, such as the loss of contact during wheel lift-off or the engagement of the pivot axle's bump stops (which does not occur in the scope of this study), ensuring the reliability of the results during the critical phase of rollover. MBD analyses aimed to find the limit tilt angle (α) in each orientation by changing the orientation angle (β) of the vehicle in the range of $\pm 180^\circ$ in 5° steps. Analyses start with a 5-second pause so that all rigid bodies can reach a static balance before tilting to avoid any undesired effect during the analyses. Then, the current orientation angle is reached in 5 s, and it is allowed to reach static balance for another 5 s. Then, the inclination angle of the platform is increased gradually (1° per second) to investigate the instability angle. Each analysis was solved in 10,000 steps. The end time of the simulation was set to 100 s to ensure the suitable step size for accurate results. In the meantime, the distance between the centre of the front axle and the middle point of the platform, and the tire forces were measured. As soon as the vertical force component of one of the wheels equals zero, the tractor overturns. Similarly, the tractor slides from the platform when the measured distance changes positively or negatively.

2.2.6. Tire model and static friction coefficient

The PAC2002 tire model was used to simulate tire behaviour. The model predicts accurately the non-linear behaviour of tires under various operating conditions by using Magic Formula. The Magic Formula, developed by Pacejka, is a mathematical formula that estimates the tire-road force interactions under different operating conditions based on basic tire properties (Martelli et al., 2023; Pacejka and Besse-link, 1997). It realistically simulates the tire forces and moments based on slip and vertical load. The static friction coefficient (f_s) between the tire and the ground directly influences the vehicle's traction behaviour and its tendency to slip. As explained in Section 2.1.4, the front wheels are attached to the platform tightly during the experiments to enable a controlled rollover, which also increases the tendency of the wheels to grip the surface. In this study, we are specifically focused on measuring the rollover angle and therefore needed to exclude the sliding phenomenon, which can occur before overturning in certain configurations, specifically extended rollover regions. This is a common practice in certification tests; for instance, ISO 16333 (2011) and (SAE International 2011) standards foresee the use of platforms with special surfaces or even employ wooden stops to achieve friction coefficients close to 1 and prevent sliding. This approach is consistent with the objective of studying and measuring the pure rollover angle, necessitating the exclusion of sliding phenomena that could otherwise occur prior to overturning in certain configurations. While it is theoretically possible to increase f_s to expand the slip-free stability regions, values greater than 1 typically represent exceptional or idealized surface conditions (Buckley, 1977). Therefore, an f_s of 1 was adopted as the highest realistic value (Müller et al., 2003; Rajamani et al., 2012) to ensure the results remain both physically plausible and safety-oriented.

2.2.7. Examining extended rollover conditions

In addition to these analyses where the f_s is used within normal limits, additional analyses were performed in order to examine the behaviour in the sliding regions. MBD analyses perform a series of equation solutions using Lagrangian-Newtonian methods to simulate the kinematic and dynamic effects in the real world (Harty and Blundell, 2015). Therefore, the results simulate the real environment conditions as realistically as possible with given circumstances. In other words, in the case covered by this study, the orientation regions where the tractor starts sliding on the platform while f_s equals to 1 are also directly reflected in the simulation. However, as mentioned before, increasing f_s will increase the gripping capacity of the tractor on the platform since the friction force is a function of the vertical force component of the tires

and the static friction coefficient f_s between the tires and the platform. Therefore, the unrealistically increased f_s will increase the lateral and longitudinal counter force on the tires, which will increase the force generated against slipping. There are currently analytical models in the literature that consider only the force components of the tractor and the overturning moments caused by these forces. Since these models do not take into account the friction forces, or in other words the longitudinal and lateral grip forces, they assume that the tractor maintains its contact with the ground until one of the vertical wheel force components becomes zero, thus, they can also calculate a theoretical overturning angle at the orientation angles where the tractor starts to slide on the platform (Carabin et al., 2025; Previati et al., 2014). In order to be able to estimate the rollover angles within these regions by using also MBD model, the analyses were repeated by increasing f_s at unrealistically high levels only for the initial CoG scenario and compared with the realistic f_s .

2.2.8. The mean absolute percentage error and model validation

The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) is then calculated to determine the error between the analyses and the real-world experiments. MAPE is an error metric that measures the accuracy of an estimation model by calculating the difference between the observed (measured) values and estimated values. While α_i^{exp} is the experimental measurement and α_i^{sim} is the simulation model result for the current orientation angle, and N is the sample number (e.g., experimentally measured orientation angles) MAPE can be calculated as follows only for the experimentally investigated orientations:

$$MAPE = \frac{100\%}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\alpha_i^{exp} - \alpha_i^{sim}}{\alpha_i^{exp}} \quad (5)$$

2.3. Possible implements and analysis scenarios

Since vineyard tractors work in narrow spaces due to the nature of their workspace, they are expected to be both highly manoeuvrable and not too wide even with implements (Pascuzzi et al., 2020). Hence, the most suitable implements are usually those mounted directly to the vehicle body. Trailed implements with tools that ensure contact with the ground, such as an extra wheel, will change the kinematics of the vehicle and affect its manoeuvrability (Wang et al., 2024a). Common implements mounted to the tractor body include spraying machines, fertilizing equipment, and pruning machines (Lazzari and Mazzetto, 2016). Spraying machines generally consist of a tank and sprayer mechanism mounted at the rear of the vehicle as can be seen in Fig. 8.a. They are used to combat diseases and harmful pests by spraying through a fan powered by the power take-off (PTO) and multiple nozzles selected according to the needs of the vineyard/orchard (McCoy et al., 2023). Fertilization equipment in Fig. 8.b is used to meet the nutritional needs of plants (Sozzi et al., 2020). Harvesting equipment facilitates the collection of grapes (Lazzari and Mazzetto, 2016). Front loaders are generally for transportation purposes (Gralak and Waluś, 2024). Trimmers may affect the CoG in longitudinal, vertical, and lateral directions as depicted in Fig. 8.c. Some symmetrical models can only affect it in longitudinal and perhaps vertical directions. Leaf removers use airflow to remove dead leaves from canopies. They are usually mounted at the front of the tractor, which means they cause a change in the CoG in the longitudinal direction. They can be single-sided or double-sided in the lateral direction according to the field need. Pruners, commonly used in vineyards, can also have a lateral asymmetric effect. Shakers used in olive gardens to harvest the olives may be mounted from behind and very close to the ground in a static position (Lazzari and Mazzetto, 2016). This would reduce the position of the CoG in the vertical direction, while a front loader might increase it besides the longitudinal direction.

In this study, the rear ground clearance of the 3-point hitch is assumed to be 700 mm, and the distance from the rear wheel centre is

Fig. 8. Mounted a. two-row sprayer (Vale Engineering Ltd., n.d., 2025), b. fertilizer (Agrex, n.d., 2025), and c. trimmer (Drury 2025).

assumed to be 800 mm. If the PTO is at the front, the distance between the connection centre and the rear wheel centre is taken as 2500 mm. Other vehicle properties are given in Table 3. Using all these variables, as well as the approximate weights and dimensions of some possible implements used with the 75 hp vineyard tractors, a CoG variation range was determined for all three directions within a certain range.

As an example, for the front longitudinal shift, the 32LA loader, which is suitable for New Holland TN and TND series, was examined. Its bucket capacity has a volume of 0.5 m³ and a lift capacity of 1500 kg to full height at pin. However, for a more realistic scenario, the lift capacity of 1045 kg to full height at 800 mm is considered to calculate the rate of maximum front shift in the x-axis. This scenario changes the CoG forward on the x-axis by 40 % of the wheelbase. However, such excessive CoG changes are balanced by ballasts (additional balancing weights), typically mounted on the opposite side of the vehicle to ensure an even distribution of axle load. Hence, the front longitudinal direction CoG shift was assumed to be 20 % of the total wheelbase. In this way, no front axle load was greater than 60 % of the vehicle load in any scenario. For the rear longitudinal shift, the mounted sprayers were considered. The total weight of the sprayer was assumed to be 600 kg with a 400 L tank capacity when the tank is full. That leads to a 17 % rearward longitudinal shift in CoG position. Since its centre is also higher than the 3-point hitch connection, which is almost at the same height as the CoG position of the tractor, it also increases the vertical position by 10 %. To investigate the CoG change in the lateral direction, the leaf remover was selected due to its ability to be mounted symmetrically and non-symmetrically. In case they are single-sided, the CoG will change in the lateral direction. Since they are usually mounted in low positions, the CoG will be lower or will remain at a similar height. However, some models with top frames can raise the position of the CoG. Studies have shown that tractors are more unstable in the lateral direction than in the longitudinal orientation (Carabin et al., 2025; Jang et al., 2022; Karaca et al., 2025; Mazzetto et al., 2013; Previati et al., 2014). Therefore, if an implement that will cause a change in the lateral direction is to be used, it is not desired to be over a certain weight and dimensions according to the capacity of the tractor. For this reason, the lateral CoG change

scenario is limited to 10 %. Possible properties of some of the implements can be seen in Table 3.

Considering these approximate values are the extreme scenarios, four analysis scenarios were considered in each direction, i.e., the maximum change of each implement and half of these values. Analysis scenarios were created by shifting the CoG position by ± 10 % and ± 20 % of the wheelbase along the longitudinal direction and ± 5 % and ± 10 % of the front axle trackwidth along the lateral direction. In the vertical direction, the initial CoG was changed by -10 %, ±20 %, and + 40 % of the initial CoG height. In the case where the mass is positioned 40 % lower, the centre of mass of the vehicle remains lower than the centre of the rear axle, hence, the lower CoG changes were limited by 20 %. Notations for all the possible scenarios are given in Table 4. The mass was considered constant for all scenarios, i.e., the unloaded tractor mass was considered. Although this situation affects the tire deflection that may be caused by more load and the relative angle between the body and the axle (Fig. 9), it can be said to be at a negligible level as the tire deflection has a parabolic characteristic in terms of vertical load and more relative load is required to create the same deflection under increased load (Jazar, 2014). This phenomenon is affected also by the tire pressure (Bietresato and Mazzetto, 2022).

3. Results

In the first stage of this study, the CoG position and mass of the tractor were determined through experimental methods. The front-rear axle load distribution of the 2355 kg tractor is approximately 2/3. This situation is compatible with the characteristic feature of tractors with pivotal front axle construction (Carabin et al., 2025). The CoG position of the tractor was measured as 11 mm on the right side with a low amount of asymmetry in the lateral (y-axis) direction and 676 mm above the ground in the vertical (z-axis) direction. The measured CoG with the other scenarios is given in Table 5.

Table 3
Estimated properties of the possible implement for a 75hp vineyard tractor.

Implement	Front loader	Rear sprayer	Leaf remover
Mass (kg)	1045	600	200
CoG distance of the implement from rear axle centre in longitudinal (x) direction (mm)	3500	-900	3000
CoG distance of the implement from vehicle central plane in lateral (y) direction (mm)	0	0	±1200
CoG height of the implement (z) (mm)	3000	1000	800

Table 4
CoG variation scenarios and notations for stability analysis.

Variation axis	Ratio and direction			
Longitudinal (x-axis) shift	20 % rear direction	10 % rear direction	10 % front direction	20 % front direction
	X _{R,20}	X _{R,10}	X _{F,10}	X _{F,20}
Lateral (y-axis) shift	10 % left direction	5 % left direction	5 % right direction	10 % right direction
	Y _{L,10}	Y _{L,5}	Y _{R,5}	Y _{R,10}
Vertical (z-axis) shift	20 % down direction	10 % down direction	20 % up direction	40 % up direction
	Z _{D,20}	Z _{D,10}	Z _{U,20}	Z _{U,40}

Fig. 9. Tractor leaning mechanics for lateral rollover for a. the idealized condition and b. the actual condition.

Table 5
Measured centre of gravity and defined variation scenarios.

Direction	Scenarios			
Longitudinal	$X_{R,20}$	$X_{R,10}$	$X_{F,10}$	$X_{F,20}$
	(504, 11, 676)	(610, 11, 676)	(1022, 11, 676)	(1228, 11, 676)
Lateral	$Y_{L,10}$	$Y_{L,5}$	$Y_{R,5}$	$Y_{R,10}$
	(805, -83, 676)	(805, -36, 676)	(805, 58, 676)	(805, 105, 676)
Vertical	$Z_{D,20}$	$Z_{D,10}$	$Z_{U,20}$	$Z_{U,40}$
	(805, 11, 946)	(805, 11, 608)	(805, 11, 811)	(805, 11, 946)
Initial CoG	(805, 11, 676)			

3.1. Rollover stability Index and stability maps

In light of the data obtained, an MBD model was created and verified through experiments. The experimental stability angles were determined only for the initial CoG position. The MBD model predicted lower rollover angles in all orientations compared to the experimental results;

indicating that it makes conservative predictions that fall within a safety margin as depicted in Fig. 10.a.a. The light and dark blue bars represent the experimental and simulation results respectively while red bars present the Absolute Percentage Errors (APE) between the two methods. The reason for this error might be the tire behaviour caused by load transfer, the differences in the CoG position that may occur in liquid tanks other than the fuel tank (for example, the CoG dynamically changes due to the liquid surface remaining parallel to the ground), and the mechanical properties of the platform (gripping capacity of the platform surface). Considering 12 orientation angles (from -60° and from $+60^\circ$ to $+135^\circ$ with 15° steps) were experimented, the MAPE of all experimental orientation configurations was 11 % with experimental angles consistently higher than the simulated ones. This indicates that the simulation results tend to underestimate rollover angles and provide conservative estimations in favor of safety.

Experimental data and MBD model stability estimates in a stability map can be seen in Fig. 10.b. A stability map is a polar graph that characterizes the rollover characteristics of a vehicle. In these maps, the radial coordinate indicates the inclination angle (α) and the angular coordinate (β) indicates the orientation with respect to the line of

Fig. 10. a. Absolute percentage error between the experimental and the simulation results, and b. comparison of two methodologies in a stability map.

maximum slope of the terrain, thus, the rollover direction of the tractor (0° : forward, 90° : right, -90° : left, 180° : backward). The dots represent experimental results, the continuous lines show simulation results within the orientation range in which the tractor overturns without sliding and the dashed lines are the simulation results where the tractor starts to slide before rollover in the stability map. As can be clearly seen, in the sliding regions, the slope angle that the tractor starts to slide is always around 45.5° regardless of the orientation. The vehicle rolls over without sliding at angles from $+10^\circ$ to $+150^\circ$, and from -15° to -145° . Both experimental and simulation results proved that the most critical instability region is always within the lateral orientation regions. In simulations, the vehicle rolls over completely to the right at 23.6° and completely to the left at 25.4° . This is due to the slight CoG asymmetry in the lateral direction. Naturally, since the CoG is closer to the hinge point than the other side, it approaches earlier to the instability region with increasing slope angle. Therefore, RSI is different for both sides in complete lateral tilting for simulations: 58 % for complete right tilting and 61 % for complete left tilting at 10° of terrain slope, 15 % for complete right tilting and 21 % for complete left tilting at 20° of terrain slope for the simulations. The RSI value comparison for the experiments and the initial CoG scenario simulations within the limit of tested orientation range are given in Fig. 11.

The MBD model was then implemented for the cases given in Table 5. RSI values for specific near-lateral orientation angles at 10° and 20° ground slopes are provided in Table 6-8. In all cases including the initial CoG, the most critical stability loss was observed in lateral and near-lateral orientations ($\beta \approx \pm 90^\circ$). As the orientation approaches longitudinal directions ($\beta \approx 0^\circ$ or 180°), i.e., in the forward and backward directions, the rollover angle increases in all CoG configurations. When the extreme orientation angles are reached, the vehicle starts to slide without rolling over in almost every instance. Although this range varies, the α angle at which the vehicle starts to slide is consistently $\sim 45.5^\circ$ for all scenarios – the negligible differences are estimated to be the margin of error in the numerical calculations. However, under the X_R and Z_U configurations during the rear rollover orientation, the front wheels typically leave the ground simultaneously. This indicates direct rearward rollover without sliding. For all cases except for extreme longitudinal rollovers, the rear wheel above the slope angle detaches from the ground first. As longitudinal orientations approach, RSI also tends to increase alongside stability.

3.2. Theoretical rollover characteristic for extreme longitudinal orientations

Fig. 12 presents the comparison of rollover angles for different f_s values. As clearly shown, increasing f_s resulted in no significant difference in the critical rollover angles for lateral and near-lateral orientations. Therefore, the variation between the rollover angles at the tested f_s levels and the baseline case ($f_s = 1$) is negligible in these directions.

Fig. 11. RSI comparison between the experimental results and the simulations for initial CoG value.

When f_s is 1.3, complete rollover occurs in the backward orientation, while sliding continues in the forward oriented rollover cases. Further investigation was carried out to determine the minimum f_s value at which sliding no longer occurs in forward-oriented cases. This threshold was found to be $f_s = 1.7$. For friction coefficients higher than this value, rollover angles for all orientations fluctuate within a limited range (less than 1 %). These slight variations are likely due to numerical errors introduced by the step size used in the MBD simulations. In pure lateral orientations, the right pure lateral rollover angle was 23.6° for $f_s = 1$ and 1.3 , and 23.7° for $f_s = 1.7$. Similarly, the left pure lateral rollover angle was 25.4° for $f_s = 1$ and 1.3 , and 25.5° for $f_s = 1.7$. This consistent pattern continues until the sliding zones for $f_s = 1$. Within the sliding region (-155° to $+150^\circ$ and -15° to $+10^\circ$), a linear trend is observed at $f_s = 1.7$, and theoretical rollover angles can still be measured. Under this condition, the tractor loses stability at 60.4° in full forward rollover ($\beta = 0^\circ$) without sliding. In full backward rollover ($\beta = 180^\circ$), both $f_s = 1.3$ and 1.7 lead to rollover at the same angle of 49.9° .

3.3. Sensitivity of stability to CoG shifts

The effect of the change in the longitudinal direction of CoG is presented in a stability map given in Fig. 13. Here, the red and green solid lines represent the front-shifted (X_F) rollover situations, and the red and green dashed lines represent the rear-shifted (X_R) CoG change cases. Black dotted lines, however, represent the sliding regions for each of the scenarios. Some critical results can be summarized for these scenarios as follows:

- In general, the change in the percentage of CoG and the change in stability showed a similar trend. The change in CoG affected stability more in the forward-oriented lateral rollovers than in the rear-oriented lateral rollovers for all the cases.
- The RSI is higher for $X_{R,20}$ and $X_{R,10}$ scenarios than for the initial CoG condition as can be seen in Fig. 10 and Table 6, and the opposite is correct for the case $X_{F,20}$ and $X_{F,10}$. In the $X_{F,20}$ scenario, RSI drops below 0 at a 20° slope, meaning the rollover condition is already met. Because the $X_{F,10}$ starts to rollover at 18.1° slope to the right. In the same case, there is only a 2 % RSI when rolling over to the left, meaning it is almost about to overturn.
- In X_R scenarios, there is a change similar to the change rate in CoG in the forward orientations of the vehicle (around 10 % for $X_{R,10}$ and 19 % for $X_{R,20}$), while in the lateral direction, there is a decrease less than the change rate in CoG. In other words, the CoG change affected the longitudinal stability more than the lateral stability. In $X_{F,10}$ scenario, the trend is similar to the X_R scenarios. However, for $X_{F,20}$, lateral stability decreases more than 20 % for right-oriented tilting scenarios.
- The approach of CoG to the front (X_F conditions) decreased lateral stability since the CoG vector becomes closer to the edges of the stability region. As mentioned in Section 2.1, rollover moment occurs around the edges of stability triangle. Hence, as the CoG approaches the front axle, its distance to the edges of stability region decreases and tractor reaches the instability phase prior than initial CoG. Similarly, the approach of CoG to the rear (X_R scenarios) increased stability in the lateral directions. The scheme of this phenomenon is depicted in Fig. 14.
- A different characteristic was observed in backward rollovers for X_R scenarios. In these scenarios, the tractor directly rolls over instead of sliding. The main reason for this behaviour is an increase in rear axle load with the reduced distance to the edge of stability triangle as shown in Fig. 14. In this region, the rollover angle is lower than the sliding angle which is specifically related to determined static friction coefficient between the platform and the tires. As the friction force is a function of axle load and f_s , with the increased rear axle load, friction force also increases and accordingly, leads the tractor to grip the platform better than other CoG change scenarios.

Table 6

RSI values of all longitudinal change simulation scenarios for near-lateral orientations under 10° and 20° slope (To enhance the interpretability of the data, a color-coded representation was applied to the RSI value cells ranging from 0 % to 80 %: values below 0, i.e., instability condition was satisfied, were marked in red, 0 to 20 % in orange, 21 % to 40 % in yellow, 41 % to 60 % in light green, and 61 % to 80 % in dark green. Since there is no RSI value more than 80 % for considered slope angles, these values were not assigned with a color-code).

$\beta \backslash \alpha$	$X_{F,20}$		$X_{F,10}$		Initial CoG		$X_{R,10}$		$X_{R,20}$	
	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°
75	0.44	-0.13	0.52	0.04	0.57	0.14	0.61	0.22	0.64	0.27
90	0.45	-0.10	0.53	0.05	0.58	0.15	0.61	0.22	0.64	0.27
105	0.49	-0.01	0.56	0.12	0.60	0.20	0.63	0.27	0.66	0.31
-105	0.55	0.10	0.60	0.19	0.63	0.26	0.66	0.31	0.67	0.34
-90	0.51	0.02	0.57	0.14	0.61	0.21	0.63	0.27	0.65	0.31
-75	0.50	0.01	0.56	0.12	0.60	0.21	0.63	0.27	0.66	0.31

Table 7

RSI values of all lateral change simulation scenarios for near-lateral orientations under 10° and 20° slope (To enhance the interpretability of the data, a color-coded representation was applied to the RSI value cells ranging from 0 to 80 %: values below 0, i.e., instability condition was satisfied, were marked in red, 0 to 20 % in orange, 21 % to 40 % in yellow, 41 % to 60 % in light green, and 61 % to 80 % in dark green. Since there is no RSI value more than 80 % for considered slope angles, these values were not assigned with a color-code).

$\beta \backslash \alpha$	$Y_{R,10}$		$Y_{R,5}$		Initial CoG		$Y_{L,5}$		$Y_{L,10}$	
	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°
75	0.68	0.36	0.64	0.27	0.57	0.14	0.47	-0.05	0.31	-0.37
90	0.68	0.36	0.64	0.27	0.58	0.15	0.48	-0.04	0.33	-0.35
105	0.70	0.39	0.66	0.31	0.60	0.20	0.52	0.04	0.38	-0.24
-105	0.46	-0.09	0.56	0.12	0.63	0.26	0.68	0.35	0.71	0.42
-90	0.41	-0.18	0.53	0.06	0.61	0.21	0.66	0.31	0.69	0.39
-75	0.40	-0.20	0.53	0.05	0.60	0.21	0.66	0.31	0.70	0.39

Table 8

RSI values of all vertical change simulation scenarios for near-lateral orientations under 10° and 20° slope (To enhance the interpretability of the data, a color-coded representation was applied to the RSI value cells ranging from 0 % to 80 %: values below 0, i.e., instability condition was satisfied, were marked in red, 0 to 20 % in orange, 21 % to 40 % in yellow, 41 % to 60 % in light green, and 61 % to 80 % in dark green. Since there is no RSI value more than 80 % for considered slope angles, these values were not assigned with a color-code).

$\beta \backslash \alpha$	$Z_{D,20}$		$Z_{D,10}$		Initial CoG		$Z_{U,20}$		$Z_{U,40}$	
	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°	10°	20°
90	0.67	0.34	0.62	0.24	0.57	0.14	0.47	-0.06	0.36	-0.27
105	0.67	0.34	0.62	0.25	0.58	0.15	0.47	-0.05	0.37	-0.26
120	0.69	0.38	0.65	0.29	0.60	0.20	0.51	0.03	0.41	-0.17
-90	0.71	0.42	0.67	0.34	0.63	0.26	0.55	0.10	0.46	-0.07
-75	0.69	0.38	0.65	0.30	0.61	0.21	0.52	0.03	0.42	-0.16
-60	0.69	0.38	0.65	0.30	0.60	0.21	0.51	0.03	0.41	-0.17

The effect of the CoG change in the lateral direction gave different characteristics in two directions. As given in Fig. 15, the CoG change causes the vehicle to rollover earlier on the slope side it approaches. The factors caused by these scenarios can be summarized as follows:

- The orientation angle range at which all scenarios started to slide before rollover varies. However, the α angle at which all cases start sliding is approximately 45.5°, as in all other conditions. In contrast to the X-change scenarios, stability is more sensitive to CoG change and demonstrates different characteristics towards right or left lateral rollover scenarios.
- The right shift of CoG has a greater effect on the stability change rate on the near-left oriented rollover compared to the orientation scenarios approaching the right as can be seen in the stability map in Fig. 16. The left shift, however, showed a similar change trend in both near-right and near-left scenarios. In the case of a right shift of

CoG, more than 3-fold stability angle decreases are observed for right-lateral overturning orientations: an average of 18 % change for $Y_{R,5}$ and an average of 37 % change for $Y_{R,10}$. In left overturning, it caused an increase in stability of around 15 % and 29 %, respectively. In the $Y_{R,10}$ scenario, the right lateral critical instability angle decreased to 14.6°, while the left lateral critical instability angle increased to 32.7°. For $Y_{R,5}$, these values are 19.3° and 29.1°, respectively. In the Y_L scenarios, the change rate of right and left overturning is somewhat more homogeneous and similar: It can be said that it is around 17 % and 33 % on average for $Y_{L,5}$ and $Y_{L,10}$. $Y_{L,10}$ increased the right overturning instability angle to 31.1°, while decreasing the left overturning angle to 17°. For $Y_{L,5}$, these values are 27.4° and 21.3°, respectively.

- At 10° of terrain slope, RSI of all scenarios is higher than zero as depicted in Fig. 15, that means the tractor maintains its stability. However, at 20° of slope, the Y_R scenarios generally have RSI values

Fig. 12. Stability map comparison for the realistic f_s scenario and an excessive f_s scenario.

below zero in the right-oriented lateral rollover scenarios. Similarly, the $Y_{L,10}$ scenario has RSI value below zero in the left-oriented lateral rollover scenarios. The rollover angle remained below 20° within the orientation angle range of $+35^\circ$ and $+120^\circ$ for the $Y_{R,10}$ scenario, and within $+65^\circ$ to $+105^\circ$ for $Y_{R,5}$ scenario. Similarly, the rollover angle remained below 20° within the orientation angle range of -45° and -110° for the $Y_{L,10}$ scenario, and $Y_{L,5}$ scenario always satisfies the rollover angle above 20° . The rollover angle is always greater than 20° for the initial CoG scenario.

- A parabolic trend was observed in the RSI variation across scenarios, with the maximum divergence consistently appearing when the CoG was shifted towards the downslope direction. This suggests a progressively increasing sensitivity of rollover stability to CoG shifts aligned with slope direction. As can be clearly seen in Fig. 15, the left CoG shift scenarios influenced the RSI variation more sensitively than the right shifts during left-oriented rollover, and the right CoG shift scenarios influenced the RSI variation more sensitive than the left shifts during right-oriented rollover.

Fig. 13. Stability map comparison (left) and RSI values of pure lateral rollover condition under certain slope angles (right) for longitudinal CoG shift scenarios.

Fig. 14. Top view of the tractor stability region for the longitudinal CoG shift scenarios on a sloped terrain and the directions of the gravity force vectors while forward-oriented lateral (left), pure lateral (middle-left), rearward-oriented lateral (middle-right) and extreme rearward-oriented (right) tilting scenarios.

Fig. 15. Top (left and middle) and front (right) view of the stability region on sloped terrains and the directions of the gravity force vectors while rearward-oriented (left) and forward-oriented (middle) right rollover cases for the lateral CoG shift scenarios, and the pure lateral left rollover case for the vertical CoG shift scenarios (right).

Fig. 16. Stability map comparison (left) and RSI values of pure lateral rollover condition under certain slope angles (right) for lateral CoG shift scenarios.

In the Z direction, as expected, moving the CoG up decreased stability, while moving it down increased stability. The main reason for this is that the increased CoG position causes the gravity force vector of the vehicle to be closer to the hinge point of the rollover as explained in Section 2.2 and can be seen in Fig. 15. The stability map and RSI comparisons of these scenarios are given in Fig. 17. Some critical findings of these scenarios are as follows:

- In the Z_U scenarios, as the rear-oriented rollover orientations are approached, sliding does not occur as in the other scenarios, the front wheels of the tractor lose contact with the ground simultaneously and complete rollover is observed. In the $Z_{U,20}$ scenario, the tractor slides in a part of the $-155^\circ - +155^\circ$ orientation range. However, within the $-170^\circ - +170^\circ$ range, the front wheels leave the ground simultaneously, and the tractor rolls over without sliding. In the $Z_{U,40}$ scenario, there is no sliding in the backward-oriented rollover simulations, both front wheels leave the ground while the platform is

Fig. 17. Stability map comparison (left) and RSI values of pure lateral rollover condition under certain slope angles (right) for vertical CoG shift scenarios.

tilting, hence rollover occurs. The highest instability angle in the backward rollover orientations of this scenario is 42.7° at the 155° orientation. This angle reduces to 40.4° for pure rearward rollover scenario.

- For the $Z_{U,40}$ scenario, which gives the lowest critical α angle values, the instability angle in the lateral rollover shows a dramatic decrease and the rollover condition is met at 17.2° to the left and 15.8° to the right pure lateral rollovers. For this scenario, the RSI always remains below 0 at 10° and 20° slope angles. For the pure lateral tilting conditions, the stability decreases between the initial CoG, and this scenario are at around 32 %. For the $Z_{D,20}$ scenario, which is the safest scenario among vertical shift cases, the rollover criteria were satisfied at 30.3° and 32.4° for right and left pure lateral tilting orientations, respectively. For these tilting conditions, the stability increases of the initial CoG, and this scenario are at around 28 %. This shows that the increase in stability when CoG moves downward is more effective than the decrease in stability when it moves upward.

4. Discussion

The results obtained from the MBD analyses revealed that regardless of the lateral, vertical and longitudinal location of CoG, the most dangerous rollover situation of the tractor always occurs in the lateral or near-lateral rollover areas. Experimental tilt tests for the initial CoG location and the corresponding MBD analyses were performed only for quasi-static conditions; dynamic effects that may cause sudden inertial effects such as acceleration, braking or terrain transitions were not taken into consideration. Additionally, the model does not fully capture the complex slide-to-rollover phenomenon, as it was designed to isolate rollover angles in slip-free scenarios consistent with standardized tests. Therefore, although the model makes predictions with high accuracy and in the safe region, it should be noted that not all variables in real terrain conditions are taken into account.

The effect of longitudinal CoG shifts on lateral rollover is generally

limited. However, a higher load on the front axle reduces stability. On the other hand, increasing the rear axle weight, especially during climbing movements, has the potential to cause a tip-over problem. In scenarios where the CoG location approaches the rear axle and changes vertically upwards, the tractor tended to roll over without slipping in backward rollovers. This indicates that more care should be taken when using rear-mounted equipment during a climbing movement. This situation significantly increases the risk of rollover in narrow and sloping terrain. The use of implement that increases the rear axle load increases lateral stability. Similarly, the increase in the front axle load decreases lateral stability. Therefore, when using front-mounted equipment such as a front loader, lateral slopes should be approached with caution and movements that may cause sudden changes in inertia should be avoided.

Lateral and near-lateral stability is deeply sensitive to CoG displacements in the lateral axis. These shifts can have proportionally greater effects on stability than expected. This is consistent with the fact that the stability losses resulting from the use of lateral asymmetric equipment such as leaf removers are proportionally greater than the CoG shifts in this axis. Although such equipment increases stability in scenarios where the equipment is above the tractor on a sloped terrain, it causes a considerable loss of stability in the other direction. Therefore, it is of great importance for stability to always orient the implement in the uphill direction when using asymmetric equipment. In addition, to increase stability, the tractor orientation can be adjusted to remain below the implement according to the slope direction. In the case of asymmetrical equipment, the use of ballast to balance the weight of the entire system will also contribute to stability behaviour.

The effect of vertical CoG shifts is clear: stability decreases as the CoG height increases. This effect applies to both lateral and longitudinal stability. However, it has been observed that longitudinal stability generally has a sufficient safety margin and the risk in this orientation remains relatively low. Therefore, the effect of vertical CoG height becomes mainly more critical in terms of lateral stability. For example, lifting a load to a height of 1.5 m of a fully loaded front loader can significantly increase the risk of rollover by reducing the lateral stability

angle from 23.6° to less than 16°. As expected, high-mounted implements reduce stability, while low-mounted ones increase it. However, low-mounted implements increase the orientation area in which the tractor can slide without rolling over in longitudinal orientations. As a result, combinations of narrow track width and high CoG should be avoided; For high mounted equipment, vertical CoG height limits should be set, and the CoG position should be reduced with suitable ballasts.

5. Conclusions

This study investigates the effect of CoG change on rollover stability of a vineyard/orchard tractor in case of an implement being used by using MBD simulations. It systematically isolates and evaluates the influence of pure CoG shifts (longitudinal, lateral, vertical) on static rollover stability under identical conditions without considering the implement geometry and provides a generalized knowledge that is applicable for wide range of implements. Carabin et al. (2025) introduced an extensive perspective on stability and discussed the functionality of a specialized test-rig for extensive tilt tests. This study used this validated test rig to tune the MBD model for quasi-static tilt tests. The obtained results were compared with stability maps for all orientation angles of the tractor on sloping terrains. The stability maps clearly showed the tilt angle of the tractor in the 360° orientation range; thus, it has enabled multi-dimensional risk assessment for lateral and longitudinal rollover scenarios. MBD model consistently gave lower rollover angles compared to experimental results, regardless of difficult-to-measure parameters such as tire behaviour, dynamic effects of moving liquid masses, and pivot kinematics. This shows that the model makes predictions within safe limits. The results showed that lateral and vertical shifts of CoG critically affect the risk of tractor rollover; and MBD model can be an effective tool in predicting these risks. Also, the CoG shifts caused by implements would lead to a significant stability change. In future studies, RSI-based dynamic models should be designed to provide real-time risky orientation warnings to operators. The methodology provides a solid foundation for future work. Transient analyses, including dynamic effects such as steering, braking, and ground transitions, should be carried out to investigate the full range of rollover scenarios. Furthermore, future studies should examine the effect of CoG change on slippery or loose ground conditions to better understand the slide-to-rollover dynamics. In addition, the contribution of low-pressure tires or different grouser pattern tires to stability should also be investigated. Studies should be carried out on the integration of sensor systems capable of dynamic CoG tracking into stability management. More realistic results can be obtained by developing finite element (FE) models that also consider the flexibility of the connection between the implement and the tractor. The study presents a preliminary result for the creation of a quantitative risk management methodology for the reduction of tractor rollover accidents and aims to establish a bridge between academic studies and industrial applications. The methodology is aimed to be a starting point for future studies both for simulation-based and smart agricultural applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Merve Karaca: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giovanni Carabin:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fabrizio Mazzetto:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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